

Innovative Potential of Social Networks in Blended Learning

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Abstract

Foundation of e-learning environment was created in the Technical College of Yambol. The virtual learning environment (VLE) has been created using Moodle software platform and has been applied. The multimedia courses have been created in different disciplines. In order to improve the offered e-learning system, we carry out survey on the end of each year. The participants are students – one part of them attended full-time regular education; other - extramural form of education. The inspection of the opinion of students enrolled in e-learning supported courses, in the TC – Yambol, showed that 90% of students support the idea of using forums, where they can share problems, news, discussions, give assessments, ideas, literature and etc. More than 80% of students gave positive answer about the stimulus to cooperate in learning groups and to identify themselves through that group. Creation of social network and community inside of College will give new possibilities to improve the quality of furthered work in blended learning.

Keywords: e-learning environment, blended learning, E-Learning 1.0, E-Learning 2.0, social network

1. Introduction

E-learning is a training strategy, using a wide range of technologies, tools and systems supporting knowledge and skills in time and context defined by the individual learner. E-learning comprises all forms of electronically supported learning and teaching. The information and communication systems, whether networked learning or not, serve as specific media to implement the learning process (Tavangarian et al, 2004).

The first generation of learning (really training) delivered through the web was E-Learning 1.0. It can be characterized by online course experiences. Most often these were either synchronous courses delivered using virtual classroom software or asynchronous courses (courseware) built using an authoring tool, and course content design followed a traditional training model that was development by an instructional designer. Finally, courses were typically managed through an LMS (Karrer, 2007).

Recently, more teachers and researchers pay attention to the possibilities of applying Web 2.0 technologies in education. Web 2.0 technology is applied not only in informal learning. Strategies are seeking to implement and integrated them in the formal learning process. New tools and services - blogs, micro-blogging, wiki-th, podcast programs, sharing links and resources, social networks, RSS/Atom data collection and more, encourage informal learning, joint implementation of activities and generation of content, while giving students access to a wide array of ideas (Ivanova, 2008).

2. Development of e-learning

2.1 Foundation of e-learning environment (E-Learning 1.0) and applying blended learning

Foundation of e-learning environment was created in the Technical College of Yambol. In order to improve the offered e-learning system, we carry out survey on the end of each year. The

participants are students – one part of them attended full-time regular education; other - extramural form of education. A survey is conducted to identify students' opinion about learning support components in blended learning model as well as their problems in acquire knowledge's. The survey is conducted with closed and open end questions. A five-point scale is used, with categories rated from 1 (absolutely disagree) to 5 (absolutely agree).

The blended learning model is established in Technical College of Yambol and supported by e-learning on-line materials that included different courses in Informatics, Programming languages, Information technology, Common and General Chemistry, Biochemistry, Microbiology, Ecology and etc. The results of our practice show that the performance of e-learning system improving the effectiveness of the education, as well as improving the motivation among students and teachers (Pehlivanova et al, 2009).

2.2 Students and teachers preferences and requirements about learning process

The learning process included different types of getting experience: *formal learning* – includes hierarchically structured school system that runs from primary school through the university and organized school-like programs crated in business for technical and professional training; *informal learning* – a lifelong process whereby individuals acquire attitudes, values, skills and knowledge from daily experience; *intentional learning* – an individual aim to learn something and goes about achieving that object; *accidental learning* – happens in everyday activities an individual learn something that had not intended or expected (Pampaloni, 2009).

As a result of different project works (in the Technical College – Yambol), the foundations of a technical and informational data for distant learning process took place: virtual library with didactic materials has been created (<http://tk.uni-sz.bg/edutk/>) – lectures; exercises; multimedia sources; tests; glossaries; links to other web-base on-line resources etc. This system includes over 40 subjects. In the Technical College – Yambol, Moodle represents VLE design, which is well known in the academic community. The architecture of Moodle is compatible with the hardware and software of Technical College – Yambol. In many subjects students are encourage making their own research on relevant topic that is represented by the owner and after that published on the web-site of the discipline for future use and assessment by the other students. More teachers from the College start to work with the e-materials to perform their lectures and prefer on-line quizzes for the examining the students. According to the e-learning project developed to provide additional support for teachers who are delivering or preparing e-materials, the main, requires of the teachers as skill level *Intermediate*, to provide e-materials is: “to be familiar with use of on-line social networks e.g. Facebook. Have used blogs or other online services to collaborate and share information. Understand how Web 2.0 services (e.g. blogs and social networking tools) can apply in education. Use some of Web 2.0 services outside school and for personal use. Have used virtual learning environments (VLE) in schools and uploaded information to the portal” (<http://www.triplescience.org.uk/elearning/>).

It has been discovered that one of the strongest determinants of students' success in higher education— more important than the details of their instructors' teaching styles—was their ability to form or participate in small study groups. Students, who studied in groups, even only once a week, were more engaged in their studies, were better prepared for class, and learned significantly more than students who worked on their own (Richard, 2001). In the conducted survey we have found that the students attending blended learning still appreciate the direct communication in the group. More than 80% of students gave positive answer about the stimulus to cooperate in learning groups and to identify themselves through that group (see Fig.2).

The power of group study was provided by Uri Treisman more than twenty years ago. As a graduate student at UC-Berkeley in the late 1970s, Treisman worked on the poor performance of African-Americans and Latinos in undergraduate calculus classes. He discovered the problem was

not these students' lack of motivation or inadequate preparation but rather their approach to studying. In contrast to Asian students, who, Treisman found, naturally formed "academic communities" in which they studied and learned together, African-Americans tended to separate their academic and social lives and studied completely on their own. Treisman developed a program that engaged these students in workshop-style study groups in which they collaborated on solving particularly challenging calculus problems. The program was so successful that it was adopted by many other colleges (Uri, 1992).

Figure 2. Students prefer direct communication in the group

The inspection of the opinion of students enrolled in e-learning supported courses, in the TC – Yambol, showed that 90% of students support the idea of using forums (fig. 3), where they can share problems, news, discussions, give assessments, ideas, literature and etc. According to students opinion the forum replace the "direct communication in the group" in some way or in this way the communication continue but in virtual space. Despite of those students doesn't attend actively created e-learning forums. They prefer to enter and use Facebook, where they created College page and dynamically exchange information.

Figure 3. Do students prefer forum?

One of the main applications social networks in education is as an alternative means of communication between teachers and students and among students themselves. On the other hand create a group with different goals - from friends and supporters University faculty or to groups working on common projects. Despite that in most universities, social networks are not perceived as a means of supporting the education process (Kiryakova et al, 2011).

2.3 Social networks

Social networking is defined as a community of people who have similar interests, share similar values or a common profession. They are primarily web based and represent a range of different means of interaction between users and file sharing, messaging, chat, photos and videos, discussion groups, blogs.

Today we train young people for whom the virtual environment on the Internet is an integral part of their life. Global Information Network changes their attitudes to communication and communication training. Number of researchers working on the methodological problems explained that iGENERATION or Net-generation sets with their orientation to technology. Due to the fact that have grown up with information technology, the representatives of this generation thinking, seek information and learn differ differently than previous generations of learners. This new reality requires modern universities to adapt as quickly as possible to it; one of effective ways to change this is to use virtual space in the learning process (Tzokov, 2011).

As the source of information that students usually use for self-preparation high percent about 35% give the notebooks as main resource, for 31% the e-materials publish on the web-site are the main resource, 19% noticed Internet and only 15% mentioned the classic books as the main source of study the subject (fig. 4).

Figure 4. Source of information for the students used to prepare for the exams

Approximately 50% from students are using e-materials to prepare themselves for exam and the rest 50% prefer the classic version of notebooks and textbooks.

3 Conclusion

In order to satisfy the new trends and requirements for the fast oriented, flexible and suitable education our team apply efforts to develop and organize with the new approaches and technology the educational system. We expect that creating social networking and working in such environment students will develop abilities: to work in team; improve their communication abilities; share easy different information; have additional support from the group; change and share ideas and etc. Creation of social network and community inside of College will give new possibilities to improve the quality of furthered work in blended learning.

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